

प्रज्ञा-सारथि

प्रकाशक

त्रि.वि. प्राध्यापक संघ

एकाइ समिति

महेन्द्र बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, बागलुड

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Migration and Rural Economy in Nepal

-Tika Ram Gautam*

1. Introduction

Migration at present has become an interesting phenomenon followed by many people in Nepal. People, specially, from rural Nepal are now migrating either permanently towards urban centres and Terai region of Nepal as permanent resident or temporarily to domestic and foreign cities for better employment opportunities. Current trend of migration in Nepal has two streams; one permanent and another temporary. People who are able to smart earning from foreign employment or get rational amount from their property in the village are migrating permanently towards urban centres and Terai regions. Some people who have a little amount of cash at hand but not sufficient for new settlement are temporarily migrating to domestic cities as temporary resident. Migration has been one of the major factors of urbanization in Nepal.

Increasing trend of migration proves that people believe that they can have better lives after migration. Consequently, population pressure is increasing in urban centres and Terai regions and decreasing in rural areas. No one is concerned with those consequences of migration phenomenon in Nepal. Government is forced to supply different things of necessities to densely populated city area. It is because various protests in cities against government have immediate impact over government.

Nearly a decade ago (in 1999), I had a field survey in Kandebash VDC of Baglung district. At that time most of the seasonal migrants were to neighbouring country, India and only a few (5 persons) were abroad. Migrants from India used to return to their villages in different seasons to look after their home, children and farmland. Women, staying alone at home, had been cultivating land (both dry and irrigated) with them properly yielding better crops. They had also some cattle including goats. I found most of the families were themselves able to supply things they need daily, e.g., maize, wheat, millet, rice, beans, soybean, chilli, turmeric, garlic, onion etc. themselves.

Most of things village people need were produced themselves. Some of the things were exchanged among themselves. Only a few things like kerosene, salt and clothes were occasionally bought once a year going very far from the village. They had independent and self-reliant rural economy based on

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local production. But now the situation is drastically changed. Local production is highly decreased and replaced with so-called modern industrial production. People emphasizes on the consumption of things like noodles, biscuits, chowmen, Coca Cola, Pepsi Cola, fruit nector and others. The situation is found similar as Shrestha (2001: xxiv) mentions, "Conspicuous consumerism was rapidly on the rise. But without increased domestic production, consumerism had begun to spread to even rural areas. It had left no space uncovered". In this article I argue that temporary labour migration to foreign countries has been one of the major causes of decreasing domestic production of our rural villages. Remittance from such temporary migration is encouraging to consume modern things like television, mobile phone, readymade clothes and dry foods. It is making our villages more dependent on others rather than to promote domestic production and self reliance as it was in the past. Heavy economic dependence, loosened social structure and lack of mutual cooperation were other results of migration from sociological point of view.

2. Present Scenerio

I visited Kandebash Village Development Committee, Chaitra, 2064, for the second time, since my last visit in 1999. The time was of Constituent Assembly Election period in Nepal. I have visited all wards in the VDC this time. In this visit, I was intended to notice out what changes were going on about migration and its impact on rural socio-economic life. During my visit I found the size and nature of migration drastically changed than it was before. The volume of migration was highly increased and reached up to 203 HHs. Ethnic composition of the migrants' HHs was Brahmin 118, Kshetri 53, Kami 23, Magar 8 and Thakali 1. Total population of migrants' HHs was 1263 including 679 females. Average family size of migrants' was 6.2 and average migrants' size based on migrants' HHs was 1.4.

Old couples, young females and children were found staying at home. In my visit I found 63 male lacking HHs. Some of the young females, especially daughter in law with children, were also found outside the village. They have been to urban centres educating their children in Boarding Schools. Due to this there were 22 old couples staying alone at home. They were neither able to work hard physically nor keep cattle with them. Thus, there was shortage of agricultural labour and lack of compost manure. Agriculture was found neglected very much. Agricultural activities were found reduced by 45 percent and production by 50 percent. It was also reported that pieces of land

were left barren which were once cultivated. There were 9 households who have left their village property including house in contract without any economic benefit because they were permanently migrated to Terai region purchasing new house and land.

While walking along the villages, I asked for snacks/breakfast to the villagers. They spoke that they could provide noodles, tea, beaten rice, biscuits and other similar dry foods of industrial products. No villagers talked about things made from local products like maize, millet, wheat, potato, soybean, milk, curd, and others. Even though season was cold, cold drinks like Pepsi Cola and Coca Cola were available there at the local shops. I felt local things were almost replaced with industrial products. Local shopkeepers are supplying these things from outside. People were found prioritizing consumption of imported things in the village rather than to produce themselves. "Growth of consumerism was clearly evident. Commercial signs and billboards had mushroomed all over. Everywhere one went, competing Pepsi Cola and Coca Cola signs, along with ads for many other consumer products caught the eye" (Shrestha, 2001:xxiv).

3. Migration and Rural Economy

Despite its geographical confinement, Nepal once had a self-sufficient, though subsistence, economy. It was characterized by what is generally referred to as the domestic mode of production. Most of the population produced for household consumption rather than for market exchange. Since the country produced sufficient goods and most of its daily necessities, the external dependence was limited to items like salt, kerosene and spices (Regmi, 1971). People used to buy only a few things like salt, kerosene from market going very far from their homes walking for few days (7-15) once in a year. The remaining things they need were produced by themselves in their own home.

Today, the economic situation is totally different. Typified by the agrarian mode of production, the economy is completely dependent on external development resources (Shrestha, 2001:10). Underdevelopment and a rapidly growing population of Nepal had reached 23 million, with 88 percent of the population residing in rural areas (CBS, 2001). Agriculture was the main source of livelihood of these people before. But now foreign employment has become an important highly prioritized new source of income.

Current trend of migration differs in the sense that previously most of the poor peasants migrated to India and very few in foreign countries as labour work.

But now upper and middle class people including poor are competing to go foreign countries for better employment opportunities for cash income. Village people looked successful to smart earning. This remittance is not ultimately contributing to strengthen rural economy but making people able to afford all the industrial products including Pepsi Cola, Coca-Cola and others (called soft and hard drinks) motivating them as modern life styles. Besides this, migration has some impacts in rural economy which are explained here from sociological point of view.

1. Neglect of Agriculture

Village people use to buy all things from local shop. They consume rice and *dal* imported rather than their own local production. Maize, wheat and millet production is found decreased by 50 percent. Village people argue that no one comes to search for corn, millet and wheat. It is because consumption of imported rice is highly increased. Some people (60 percent) argue that consuming foods from corn, millet, wheat other local things is now supposed to be traditional and poor ones. No body intends to consume those domestic things as they have cash from remittance and want to become modern and rich. Therefore agriculture has now been totally neglected in the village.

Only few people want to continue their agricultural occupation. But they complain about shortage of labour. On the one hand there are only a few young people left in the village. Those youths who are in the village are not willing to go for labour work. Thus few people who are continuing their traditional agricultural occupation did not get agricultural labour to work in the farm. The conclusion made by Ellingsen (2001:237) contrasts here. "The local labour demand created by migration also provides income opportunities for poor peasants, making their seasonal migration unnecessary". It was slightly true in the past. In my previous study it was found as explained by Ellingsen (2001:233), "Remittances thus reinforce landownership, stabilize existing property and can be used to purchase fertilizers and high yielding varieties of seed "

In my previous study I found labour migration to India had increased the value of land because those seasonal migrants used to purchase land if they had some money. The farm had more agricultural value then. But today the price of land is very lower as compared to then. I found the value of land decreased by 50 percent¹ now. Some migrants' who are able to earn little more are purchasing new home and land in new places. Thus value of land has been decreased and agriculture is completely ignored.

tions or tie among village people was very strong. But today people use to buy things, most in need, from local shop and market. They could have anything they need if they had money. It was the feeling of 75 percent migrants' families. It is also due to remittance. Thus, remittance from migration and consumerism has made mutuality among village people weaker today.

4. Lack of Human Resource and Cash in the Village

It is true that large amount of remittance is introducing in Nepalese villages. All the necessities are now fulfilled with that cash. Village life is completely resting on remittance. There was cash running in the village. But now reality is different from that of past. In the past the situation was similar to Ellingsen's (2001:236) findings that permanent migration was an almost unknown phenomenon". But today migrant's families with little amount of remittance is spent on things of daily needs and the rest on purchasing new land and house. Then they migrate permanently to new places. This year 12 migrant's families are found migrated to Terai region i.e. Chitwan and Nawalparasi. Thus migrants who have some amount of income are either spending it temporarily migrating to urban centres or purchasing piece of land and house in new places. Besides this most of the villagers are spending their cash in buying things of daily need. This phenomenon has caused lack of human resource and cash the village.

5. Devaluation of Local Resources and things

There are two types of resource in village. Physical labour is human resource and land, forest and water are natural resource. There is shortage of labour in the village because most of youths are migrated. Very few if left in the village they get no work to be done. People left keeping cattle and cultivating land. The value of land and jungle is also decreased. The result is no body buys land and grass land today even in very low price. People migrating permanently are leaving their land, grassland and house free of cost. Similarly few things produced in the village e.g. maize, millet, wheat and other have no price because no body consumes it. Thus local resource and things are devaluated now.

4. Conclusion

Migration has become an interesting and essential phenomenon in both rural villages and urban cities in Nepal. People from rich and poor class, rural and

urban centres, Himal, Mountain and Terial region are temporarily migrating to foreign cities for cash income. Trend of this temporary migration is highly increasing. There are 283 migrants in one VDC which proves highly increased migration as one of the best alternative to earn cash. Though migration is providing cash needed in the village it has some adverse effects. It has discouraged production and consumption of domestic local products encouraging consumption of capitalistic industrial production. We can find increased consumerism in village. Agriculture is neglected. External dependency is increasing. Mutual cooperation is now replaced with unfair competing in consumption of so called modern industrial products. Migrants' with smart earning are permanently leaving villages causing population imbalances including lack of quality human resource. Similarly value of local resource and things is highly devaluated. Thus migration to foreign countries is deteriorating our domestic rural economy highlighting consumerism. Trend of migration of should be controlled and consumption of domestic things should be prioritized to promote rural economy. If it is unchecked in time rural economy will be completely destroyed in near future without providing any things to common people.

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विजयादशमी तथा शुभदीपावली
२०६५ को सुखद् उपलक्ष्यमा सम्पूर्ण
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सम्पूर्ण शुभचिन्तक
महानुभावहरुमा सुख, शान्ति एवम्
समृद्धिको हार्दिक मंगलमय
शुभकामना व्यक्त गर्दछौं ।

ओमप्रसाद शर्मा

सभापति

तथा

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महेन्द्र बहुमुखी क्याम्पस, बागलुङ